

A REVIEW ON BIOETHANOL PRODUCTION FROM AGRICULTURAL MATERIALS

P. D. I. Ebienfa, and B.E. Yabefa

Department of Agricultural and Environmental Engineering, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Amassoma, Bayelsa State.

Email: yabefabranly@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT: Bioethanol is a type of biofuel produced by the fermentation of organic materials such as crops and agricultural wastes. In this study, the production of ethanol from various agricultural materials have been reviewed. Some examples of feedstock for ethanol production include; corn, sugarcane, potatoes, cassava etc. The process of ethanol production is normally done in different including pretreatment, hydrolysis, fermentation distillation, dehydration. The ethanol produced from agricultural materials as feedstock can be used fuel in vehicles that use the petroleum based gasoline. However, literature is scarce on the review of bioethanol from agricultural materials. Therefore, this study intends to discuss the production of bioethanol from agro-materials.

Keywords: bioethanol, biomass, pretreatment, fermentation, substrates

INTRODUCTION

Fossil fuel depletion and global warming brought on by greenhouse gas emissions from using fossil fuels are currently motivating academics to create more environmentally friendly fuel alternatives, due to the very high demand of fuel across the globe (Oberoi et al. 2011). There are many possibilities under consideration, including biofuels. Based on the properties of bioethanol, it is regarded as the most potential biofuel to replace gasoline. When monomeric sugar from sources of carbohydrate like corn etc. is fermented by microorganisms, then, a liquid oxygenated fuel that has oxygen of about thirty-five percent is created (Edeh, 2021). Bioethanol is normally produced from agricultural biomass, hence, it is an environment friendly type of fuel that is renewable unlike the gasoline and other petroleum based fuel products. The bioethanol is a more purified fuel due to the fact that, the combustion of bioethanol does not step up the footprint of the carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere, but the CO₂ produced is normally made to be carbohydrates by conversion in the bioenergy crop using the sunlight energy through a process called photosynthesis, and the cycle is continues. Blending ethanol with gasoline has a number of benefits. It raises the level of octane. In contrast to lead and other fuel additives, ethanol is non-toxic. When gasoline/ethanol blend is burned, it may emit less carbon monoxide and other pollutants than regular gasoline since ethanol contains oxygen. Additionally, the generation of biofuel from plants to replace gasoline will boost economic growth. Accordingly, the production of biofuels particularly bio-ethanol has become strategically

significant (Chovau et al., 2013). One of the major producer and exporter of oil is Nigeria. Nigeria is ranked seventh in the world for oil exports and 12th for oil production. According to the EIA (2009), the country's natural gas reserves were 184 trillion cubic feet, its oil output exceeded 2.2 million barrels per day, and its proven oil reserves were assessed to be 36.2 billion barrels as of May 2009. Despite having substantial proven oil reserves, the country still imports refined products like gasoline, diesel, and kerosene to meet domestic demand. This situation is brought on by the low capacity of domestic refineries and the unpredictable supply of crude oil to refineries due to sociopolitical unrest in Nigeria's oil province, the Niger Delta. The frequent vandalism of pipelines that carry crude oil from offshore and coastal oilfields to onshore refineries is the main cause of refinery spills and shortages. The supply of refined goods to Nigeria is extremely variable, leading to periodic shortages, as a result of inadequate logistics and fluctuating crude oil prices in international markets. Nigeria's main goal is to encourage domestic biofuel production in order to lessen its reliance on imported refined goods. By replacing gasoline with bioethanol, liquefied petroleum gas with biogas, and then, diesel with biodiesel, Nigeria can lessen its reliance on imported refined petroleum products, save foreign exchange, address the issue of unstable foreign supply, and preserve its depleting oil reserves. Furthermore, Nigeria's need to diversify her energy sources has long been recognized (Nwachukwu & Lewis, 1986).

It is envisaged that as biofuels become more widely employed, the nation's energy basis will become less vulnerable to political unrest. Furthermore, bioenergy feedstock is readily available and abundant in Nigeria. However, because of the high dependence on the oil resources in the early 1970s, agriculture which had been the nation's backbone and the primary employer of labor since independence in 1960 was overlooked in favor of petroleum. Poor agricultural productivity and high unemployment rates, particularly in rural regions, led to a high rate of urban drift. The primary force behind the government's efforts to buck this trend is biofuel.

Therefore, Nigeria's entry into the sector of bioenergy is a way to boost agriculture, especially in the rural sub-sector. According to Azih (2007), among other things, the Nigerian biofuel initiative aims to increase agricultural opportunities and create a multiplier on employment generation, especially in the rural sector. Since the publication of the policy on biofuels in 2007 at the national level, some agencies of the government at federal level, has created markets for ethanol by replacing conventional gasoline with a 10% ethanol blend and kerosene with ethanol gel fuel. These actions have immediately created a demand of 5.14 billion liters of ethanol annually.

. The aim of this study is to extensively make a review of the benefits and agricultural byproducts in bioethanol production. We also want to look at the current biofuel production and their feedstock.

2. PROCESS OF BIOETHANOL PRODUCTION

The production of bioethanol is done by the conversion of organic matter into ethanol. The ethanol is a biofuel which can be used to power vehicles. The feedstocks for ethanol production include plants such as corn, sugarcane, switch grass, and other sources of biomass. Also, agricultural waste materials such as crop residues, wheat straw etc. can be used as feedstock for ethanol production. Hence, feedstocks for ethanol production can be grouped into lignocellulosic materials, substrates and starchy materials. The conventionally used processes of ethanol production include; pretreatment which has to do with the breaking down of complex carbohydrate in to simple

sugar, then, the next step is the conversion of the pretreated biomass into fermentable sugar (hydrolysis). Then, micro-organisms are used to convert sugars into ethanol, then followed by distillation and dehydration.

2.1 Lignocellulosic materials

A wide range of agricultural biomass is covered by lignocellulosic materials, which are less expensive than traditional agricultural feedstock and can be produced with less energy, fertilizer, and pesticide use. Biofuels made from lignocellulosic biomass have minimal greenhouse gas emissions and lessen the effects of climate change and other environmental issues. Maize silage (Oleskowicz-Popiel et al., 2008), paper sludge (Marques et al., 2008), and barely hull (Kim et al., 2008) are examples of lignocellulosic materials used in the production of ethanol.

The lignocellulosic biomaterials have lignin content, and are poor in porosity and highly crystalline in nature, hence they are difficult to be handled, hence, techniques have been studied by different researchers for the pretreatment of lignocellulosic materials for ethanol production, which include acid treatment, steam treatment, and alkali treatment (Hu and Wen, 2008). The ethanol production from lignocellulosic biomass has so many advantages, but, since, there are no facilities for such massive production is the major challenge (Feria et al. 2011). Presently, the most conventional feedstock for ethanol production are starch-based material in which a liquefaction step is involved to make the starch soluble, thus making available for conversion to fermentable sugar, and the hydrolysis step for glucose production from starch, which is finally fermented to ethanol (Zhang et al. 2013). The production of ethanol from the lignocellulosic materials and starch based materials have some similarities in the processes of production, but lignocellulosic-based conversion is facing more difficulties due to technical and economic related constrains Mood et al. 2013). **Figure 1** presents the flow chart of ethanol production from lignocellulose material.

Figure 1: Flowchart of ethanol production

2.2 Substrate Materials

Different kind of substrate materials can be used to produce ethanol. The substrate used for ethanol production is considered based on the availability of the material in the locality. Another consideration is the cost implication involved in using the material. Some substrates are sucrose containing materials, because ethanol is produced by

fermentation which is a process to convert sugar to ethanol. Sucrose containing materials could make the process of ethanol production easy. Some examples of such substrates include sugarcane, sorghum, sugar beet etc. Sugarcane is a major substrate for ethanol ethanol production around the world (Goldemberg et al., 2008). Sugar sorghum is another viable crop containing sucrose, which can be used for ethanol production (Giorgis et al, 1997).

2.3 Starch Containing Materials

Ethanol can as well be produced from starchy materials. Sugar can be produced from starch by conversion in a process called saccharification, it is then fermented, and then distilled to produce ethanol. An example of a starchy material for ethanol production include corn, because, to produce a starch that is pure and have high quality is easily possible. using corn as feedstock. Ethanol can be produced from any starch containing crop or plants. Using a system expansion method to net energy analysis, Gulati et al. (1996) looked into producing ethanol from domestic maize grain. This study includes the following production systems such as the production of urea to estimate the net energy associated with the ethanol produced from corn, soybean products from soybean milling, ethanol production from corn dry and wet milling. There is interdependence among these five product systems. All of these systems, in other words, produce goods that either compete with or replace every other similar commodity on the market. The products' displacement ratios evaluate how well their marketplace functions match up. Regardless of the ethanol production process used, the net energy, including transportation to consumers, is 0.56 MJnet/MJ of ethanol from maize grain. Domestic usage of fossil fuels, especially petroleum, might be decreased by using ethanol as a liquid transportation fuel. Due to the large variety of possible process energy values, process energy related to wet milling, dry milling, and the corn agriculture process also has a considerable impact on net energy. Allocation processes in the foreground system of ethanol production from maize grain can be totally eliminated using the system expansion approach. Numerous studies have examined the synthesis of ethanol from a variety of starchy materials, including wheat (Murphy & Power, 2008), cassava (Leng et al., 2008), sweet potatoes (Quintero et al., 2008), and potatoes (Quintero et al., 2008). Ethanol can be produced from starchy materials by dry milling or wet milling

2.3.1 Dry Milling

The dry milling can be simply described as a process of crushing the plant materials like grains in to smaller particles without using water. This is a more conventional and efficient method of ethanol production

Figure 2: A Flowchart of dry milling (Kim et al., 2008)

2.3.2 Wet Milling

This is method used in breaking down the plant materials in to their component parts such as starch, fibers, and protein. Wet milling involves the process of soaking the grains or plant materials inside water to make it soft before grinding to release the desired components. The various components of grain are separated in wet milling before saccharification.

Figure 3: A Flowchart of wet milling (Saunders et al., 2001)

3. CONCLUSION

In this study, the production of ethanol from various agricultural by-products have been reviewed. The process of ethanol production involves different stages such as pretreatment, hydrolysis, fermentation distillation, dehydration. Ethanol is produced from lignocellulose materials, substrate materials and starchy materials. The various kind of substrates used for ethanol production varies with different countries because of their different conditions of farming. Some examples of feedstock for ethanol production include; corn, sugarcane, potatoes,

cassava etc. The ethanol produced from agricultural feedstock can be comfortably used in place of the petroleum based gasoline.

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